

THE ROLE OF TEMPERAMENT IN ADAPTATION TO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. Temperament is part of the biologically determined structures of the individual. Temperament determines the existence of many psychological differences between people, as well as in emotions, emotional impressionability, rhythm and speed of actions, and other dynamic characteristics. This article talks about the role of temperament in the adaptation of primary school students to the educational process.

Key words: Temperament, choleric, melancholic, sanguine, phlegmatic, temperament, mobility.

Introduction

The reforms carried out in the education system in our republic, at the same time, set the task of training responsible, willing, devoted to their profession, dedicated personnel in this system. At the present time, the sharp changes in the development of the society impose qualitatively new and relatively complex tasks, in which the level of development of a person's intellect, the regulator of his mental capabilities, and moral aspects are of particular importance. Today, as in all fields, special attention is paid to the field of science, including psychology. It is the self-awareness of the individual, the understanding of his identity, the formation of human character and temperament that develops from childhood.

In the science of psychology, we can see that temperament is fully explained from the psychological characteristics of a person. Temperament, psychologically speaking, is an individual characteristic that manifests itself in a person's emotional impulses and general behavior in a person. The speed, strength and stability of emotional arousal in each person is different. Some people's emotions are quick, strong and stable. In some people, such arousal is slow, weak and does not go far. Such characteristics of temperament are especially evident in the involuntary reactions of the organism in response to the influence of the surrounding environment, along with the emotional arousals in a person. These characteristics are externally visible in a person's facial expressions, pantomimes, involuntary actions and gestures. Such arousal characteristics of a person's emotions are reflected in the strength and stability

of attention, the qualities of the will, mental processes, including the speed of speech.

Depending on how such involuntary activity occurs, we call some people "quick", "restless", "energetic", "enthusiastic". We call some of them "slow down", "lapashang" and so on. A person's temperament (customer) is formed from these individual characteristics. Symptoms of certain temperaments are evident in childhood. The spiritual world of a person consists of a continuous set of actions, one of which directly leads to another, and they rule in a way similar to a continuous chain system. For the same reason, impressions of the external environment, memories of the past, creative imaginations about the future, good intentions, desires, goals and wishes, reasoning, thoughts and problems, emotional experiences, volitional qualities are present in the psyche of a person. a solid foundation for the ontogenetic world is provided by continuous exchange of places. It is observed that the progress of the spiritual world, its speed, content, form, scope, characteristic, character, quality, and mechanism are manifested in different ways in a single person. That is probably why people tend to respond to natural phenomena, social realities, factors, influence forces quickly or slowly, easily or with difficulty.

Temperament is a set of individual characteristics of a person that characterizes the dynamic and emotional state of human activity and behavior. Thus, temperament has two components - activity and emotionality. Behavioral activity characterizes the level of mobility, aspiration, speed, or, on the contrary, slowness and inactivity. In turn, emotionality characterizes the course of emotional processes, determining the sign (positive and negative) modality (joy, sadness, fear, anger, etc.).

At present, temperament type is understood not as a simple set of characteristics common to a certain group of people, but as a legal, necessary interdependence of these characteristics. The legal interrelationship of the features characterizing the temperament type can be reflected as follows. People with different temperament types have different character traits, personality traits, and situations.

The important characteristics corresponding to temperament types are shown as follows. Sanguine high reactivity. He laughs hard at things that will happen. An unimportant fact makes him very angry. He responds to everything that attracts his attention with great excitement. His gestures and movements are clearly visible. It is easy to know his mood, his relationship to things or people, based on his appearance. He concentrates his attention quickly, has low

sensitivity. The threshold of sensitivity is high, it does not notice very weak sounds and light stimuli. He is highly active, very enthusiastic and hardworking, often raises his hand in classes, can work for a long time without getting tired, and enthusiastically takes on new tasks. Activity and reactivity are balanced. It is easy to call him to discipline. He can quickly control the manifestation of his emotions and his involuntary actions. His movements are intense, his speech is fast, he starts a new job quickly, he concentrates quickly. His mind works quickly, he is resourceful. Its movements are extremely smooth. Their feelings, moods, interests and aspirations are very changeable. He gets along with new people quickly. He easily learns new requirements and new conditions. He can move quickly from one job to another. Quickly learns and quickly changes skills. He has a compact mind, extrovert. He responds to external impressions lower than his visions of the past and future life.

Choleric, like sanguine, is distinguished by low sensitivity, high reactivity and activity, but reactivity prevails over activity. That's why he's restless, restless, restless. It is slightly smoother and rougher hardened than Sanguine. That is why he has great stability and great determination in his aspirations and interests, and it is difficult to shift his attention. The mental tempo is fast. If he starts something, he will finish it, but only if he is interested in it. Phlegmatic-sensitivity is weak, emotional excitability is low, it is difficult to laugh, get angry, and break the mood. But when he laughs hard about something, he remains calm. He does not disturb his peace even in the event of a major disappointment. His gestures are few, his actions are inexpressive, he is distinguished by his enthusiasm and hard work. High activity is low, far superior to reactivity. It is distinguished by endurance, tenacity, self-control. The tempo of his movements and the tempo of his speech is slow, expressionless, he concentrates his attention slowly and shifts his attention with difficulty. Adapts to new conditions with difficulty, Introvert. He joins new people with difficulty, responds to external impressions with difficulty.

Melancholic-high sensitivity, high sensitivity (high sensory thresholds). For some small reason, tears flow from his eyes. Finally, he is irritable, he cries slowly, he is sincere, he laughs very little, he is inactive, he does not trust himself, he is shy, he washes his hands and slaps his armpits if there is a little trouble. It is not rigid. His attention is quickly distracted, he is unstable, his mental pace is slow. Rigid, introverted. Individual style of activity and temperament Individual style of activity does not arise in a person by itself, it is formed at all stages of a person's development (from kindergarten age to the

acquisition of professional skills). A person's temperament forms an individual style of activity. For the same reason, an individual style of activity means an individual system of specific and appropriate ways to achieve success for a person. A unique combination of temperament characteristics is manifested in the course of the individual style of human activity in relationships and cognitive processes. The individual style of activity depends not only on temperament, but also on other reasons, skills and qualifications formed in the process of personal experience. The individual style of activity can be considered as the adaptation of the innate characteristics of the human organism and the types of the nervous system to the operating conditions. According to the mobility of temperament, it was found that people with opposite characteristics resort to different tactics of action in the same work situation. Active people act urgently and quickly, while people with a weak temperament are distinguished by the fact that they pay a lot of attention to preparatory work, which indicates the need for urgent action.

Temperament has a direct influence on the ability of people to become leaders in a group and in the process of work.

There is no need to consider the issue of superiority of one of the temperaments. Each temperament has its positive and negative aspects. The passion, activity and energy of the choleric, the impressionability and readiness of the sanguine, the depth and stability of the feelings of the melancholic, the calmness and absence of haste of the phlegmatic - all these are the positive aspects of the mentioned temperaments. At the same time, their negative aspects can be pointed out. Sanguine temperament can lead to a tendency to light nature, feelings that are not deep enough and stable. Choleric temperament can make a person short-tempered, unable to control himself, prone to regular "explosions". A person with a melancholic temperament can be overly attached to his experiences, and extremely shy.

Children with a phlegmatic temperament are lazy, sluggish, balanced and calm people, they are not easily affected by emotions, and it is difficult to release them from themselves, their feelings are almost not manifested from the outside. without action, life can make you indifferent to all impressions.

Conclusion

Thus, temperament is an individual unique set of naturally determined mental characteristics of an individual. these characteristics include the intensity, tension, influence and rhythm of the general neuro-psychic activity, the increase and decrease of the characteristics manifested in the motor, mental and communicative sphere of the individual; includes excitability, reactivity, stability

of the subject's emotional structure, control of emotions. Temperament only determines the dynamic characteristics of activity and behavior patterns.

To sum up, human temperament depends on education, upbringing process, social world, and skills and qualifications acquired by people. Self-confidence and actions of successful people in life depend to some extent on the type of temperament.

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